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The Influence of Horoscopes on Turkish EFL Students’ Willingness to Communicate

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Abstract

It is a fact that personal features and qualities play a crucial role in determining learners' success or failure in their attempt to learn foreign languages. It was these factors that lit a bulb in the mind and opened a path to set off to find out how these features affected the learners' communication eagerness in L2. The main aim of the current study is to explore the relevance between the learners' horoscopes and their willingness to communicate utilizing a mixed-method research design. Willingness to communicate (WTC) and Self-perceived communicative competence (SPCC) surveys have been conducted for the quantitative section and a semi-structured interview with an in-depth content analysis for the qualitative part. Interestingly, no significant affect of horoscopes on students' willingness to communicate was found out, however, the interviews elaborated to some extent that among the 5 other stated horoscopes, Leos were more willing to communicate with their friends, with their classmates and with strangers.

Keywords: Willingness to Communicate, Self-Perceived Communicative Competence, Horoscopes, English Language Learning

1. Introduction

It is a fact that numerous affective factors impinge on the use of a target language in the classroom environment. Some of these factors stem from the effects of sociability, risk-taking, discomfort and the powerful influence of motivation in L2 classes, besides perspectives about the international community, tendency for L2 learning, concern for grade, etc. Studies carried out so far have indicated that EFL learners' feelings and attitudes towards L2 learning as two affective factors have an essential effect on the process of second language learning (Horwitz, 1986; Horwitz, 2001; Horwitz, & Cope, 1986; Horwitz & Young, 1991; MacIntyre & Gardner, 1989; MacIntyre & Gardner, 1991). Arising from the field of speech communication, “willingness to communicate” (WTC) is quite a recent inclusion to these affective variables. The term was used by McCroskey and associates to identify the individual's personality-based inclination to approaching or abstaining the starting of communication whenever felt free to do so (McCroskey, 1992, p. 17).

WTC, being initially put forward with reference to communication in L1, was thought to be a stable personality feature hypothesized to be stationary across various situations. However, when expanded to L2 communication situations, not limiting WTC to only a trait-like variable was suggested. Particularly because L2 usage gives a potential for important situational differences taking into account many unpredicted diversities in learners' competence and relations among groups (MacIntyre, Clément, Dörnyei, & Noels, 1998). Originating by such well-grounded theoretical knowledge, MacIntyre et al. (1998) set off to characterize WTC in a L2, a theoretical model in which individual and social context, cognitive and affective context, tendencies of motivation, settled ancestry, and behavioral disposition are interrelated in affecting WTC in a L2. Recently, numerous studies have focused on determining factors affecting L2 WTC. Herein, several elements have been identified as either indirectly or directly presumptive of WTC, including factors like perceived communicative competence, motivation, attitudes, communication anxiety, emotional intelligence, and etc.

Being that research on willingness to communicate is comparatively new, not many studies have been put forward in the Turkish EFL context. Bektaş (2005), Öz et al. (2015), and Altuner (2017) for instance, investigated whether college students in the Turkish context learning English as a foreign language were willing to communicate when they had an opportunity to do so. However, considering the relevant literature, not many studies except for Ahmed (2006) and Ragini (2019) have been carried out who set off to discover the relation between students' date of birth and their interest in English as a foreign language. Yet, the affect of the recently ascending topic horoscopes on the WTC level of students is an area uninvestigated. In this respect, the study introduces novelty.

The attempt of horoscopes to spread to almost all areas of social daily life and the fact that people at least know what their sign makes it a social issue. The fact that it can be addressed in almost all societies makes it a universal subject. As ELT practitioners, possible interventions that could be incorporated into instructional pedagogy should always be contemplated. This thought gave a prompt to conduct a study to ascertain the relevance between the horoscopes and the willingness to communicate level of students. Therefore, the present study is a research based on both qualitative and quantitative data to explore the relevance that exists between the learners' willingness to communicate and their horoscopes.

2. Literature

2.1. *Willingness to Communicate and Its Theoretical Foundations*

As Barlas (2016) puts it, Willingness to Communicate was defined by MacIntyre, Dörnyei, Clément, and Noels (1998) as “a readiness to enter into discourse at a particular time with a specific person or persons, using a L2”. It is a vital indicator of having an inner desire to speak. According to Kang's (2005) definition “Willingness to Communicate (WTC) is resolute predisposition of an individual in a specific situation, towards efficiently inoccupying in communication which might change in accordance with the conversational context, topic and interlocutor(s) among other potential situational variables.” Willingness to communicate (WTC) was defined by MacIntyre et al. (1998) as “an intention or preference to attend or start communication when given a choice to do so” (p. 5). With respect to contemporary language education, WTC in second or foreign languages has grown into one of the most specialized research areas of recent times. One of the earliest attempts to examine the nature of communication goes long way back to the years 1958 and 1959, when the psycho-sociologist Theodore Clevenger began to question the relationship between public speaking and stage fright. In this regard, an article published by Clevenger in 1959 gave inspiration to further research into attitude and avoidance in communication, and herewith was marked as groundbreaking in this area of research (McCroskey, 1982). Subsequently, Phillips (1965) studied communication apprehension and reticence in communication where he suggested that ‘reticence’ was regarded as a personality-based anxiety disorder. At the beginning, the researcher hypothesized that anxiety could be the primary reason for reticence in speech communication. However, in his following studies (1984, 1986, and 1997) he started to disapprove his previous opinion about reticence by expressing that the major reason for reticence is indeed a lack of communication skills. Phillips (1984) further claimed that although people considered as reticent in communication may not hold insufficient social skills, they actually have a tendency to think so. Latterly, it was due to Clevenger and Phillip's studies and efforts within this field that the subsequent researchers eager to carry out in-depth research into communication moved on to practice the later conceptualization of willingness to

communicate besides two well studied communication factors: Communication Apprehension (CA) and Self-Perceived Communication Competence (SPCC) (McCroskey, 1997). In respect to this, numerous distinguished scholars and linguists began to inquire into various areas of research concerning communication, for instance, McCroskey (1970) focused on communication anxiety and its major factors, Burgoon (1976) investigated unwillingness to communicate, and McCroskey and Richmond (1982) carried out studies examining shyness as an affective factor that might influence individuals' language learning process.

2.2. Horoscopes as individual difference variables

Learning a foreign language is a complex process that involves a seemingly infinite number of variables. Of the latter, a learner's personal characteristics, represented by questions like the following: "Who is the learner? How old is he? What is his intellectual capacity?, What sort of personality does he have?, etc...." form decisive factors that can bring about a great deal of variation in the interest to learn in general, and duly determine one's approach to or avoidance of learning an FL in particular. This is so because interest is of much practical value in the domain of education and has been proved to be a factor of central role in motivating people to join language courses, formal or informal, and to be enthusiastically engaged in its relevant varied activities. Accordingly, teachers of FLs are perceived to have won half of the battle if they succeed in instilling in their learners the interest to learn since a basic aspect of effective teaching involves identifying learners' interest and using it to achieve a high degree of involvement in the FL activities (Callahan, 1971: 252). Wilson (1974: 43) adds that "to feel interested in anything is to feel attracted to it, to feel inclined to give attention to it." In other words, interest involves feeling disinclined to attend to other things, and feeling vexed and uncomfortable, when prevented from giving attention to the thing being interested in. Hence, learners of limited intellectual ability, uninterested and unprepared to be engaged in the task of learning the FL have constantly demonstrated frustration and less interest to learn.

In reference to Wikipedia, the graphic illustration or representation which shows the celestial objects' (Sun, Moon and other planets) positions at the time of a person's birth is called horoscope. The words *hōra* and *scopos* in Greek mean "time" and "observer." The horoscopes are designed by astrologers when a person is born based on the alignment of planets and stars which is believed to have an impact on his or her mood, personality, behavioral traits and other factors. According to the astrological scheme, our date of birth a relationship with certain aspects of our persona to some extent.

So, recently, there has been a boost in the studies to comprehend and clarify individual personality as part of society and social interaction. Due to these studies, it is no more possible to hold apart the personality of the individual from society and social interaction. In an attempt to find out relationship between the "Date of Birth" and interest in English, Ahmed (2006) unfortunately found nothing of significance except that individuals born in the cold months were more inclined and interested to join departments of English than their counterparts who were born in the hot months.

Turkish educational institutes at all levels witness noticeable numbers of failures and dropouts due to learners' unsuccessful achievement in English. Such a phenomenon is usually attributed to loss of confidence coped with reciprocal accusations among the parties involved in the process of teaching and learning English. Although different factors of negative repercussions have often been pinpointed as responsible for such a deteriorated situation, "in recent years there has been an increasing awareness of the necessity in second language research and teaching to examine human personality in order to find out solutions to perplexing problems"(Brown, 1980: 100), at a time when the influence of learners' date of birth on their educational progress has recently been studied more closely (Johns, 1962; Jackson, 1964; Williams 1964), especially if we know that 'careful, systematic study of the role of personality in second language acquisition has already led to a greater understanding of the language learning process and to improving language teaching methods (ibid.: 101). Since, within the Turkish context, the remedial procedures have always fallen short of bringing about the required solutions, the current study endeavors to touch upon a virgin field of study within the Turkish context, that is horoscopes, which, if proved influential, may pave the way to put forward some suggestions that can minimize students' dislike of FLs, maximize their willingness to communicate and duly make the process of FL teaching and learning more appealing and fruitful.

According to Ahmed (2006), personal characteristics and qualities play a pivotal role in determining learners' success or failure in foreign languages. Likewise, since the related literature on this point is very lacking especially in terms of the educational characteristics and qualities outlined by individuals' horoscopes, and since the available material tackles the topic under discussion via the statement of time units or expressions, namely months and seasons, which do not refer precisely to the horoscopes, reference will be made to the seasons and months, and not necessarily to the horoscopes; a procedure that goes with what other researchers in the field have done. At the outset, educational progress and intellectual performance, measured by tests of ability or achievement, which vary according to the season of birth had been heeded and their influence on educational progress had been attended to very closely. For instance, Pinter (1931) and Pinter and Forlano (1933) got abundant evidence with large samples of children. They concluded that learners born in the warmer months obtained slightly higher scores than those born in the colder months. Williams (1959) showed that summer birthdays were significantly more often with a group of educationally backward children. Jenkins (1962) arrived at the conclusion that while the date of birth had not the same marked effect upon future academic performance, it nevertheless had significance. Jackson (1964) stated that the number of streams increased (i.e. in larger schools), so the difference between summer and winter born children increased. Jinks (1964) stated that the summer born children were also at a disadvantage in streamed schools. Finally, Freyman (1965) concluded that summer-born children obtained low or average marks than high marks in the yearly examinations.

A close look at what has been so far stated shows that the focal point of departure in the above-mentioned researches has been the "effect of the date of birth on learners' achievement in the domain of education at large"; a point that is beyond the scope of the present study which focuses on individuals' willingness to communicate, and in our case, in the light of an important variable, namely, the qualities and characteristics of students' horoscopes.

3. Method

The present study aims to investigate the influence of horoscopes on EFL students' willingness to communicate. Its study was carried out with 204 English Preparatory Class students studying at Necmettin Erbakan University. The student's departments varied from Aircraft Engineering to English Language Teaching. It was a study implemented in the second semester of the 2021/2022 academic year. All the students who participated in the study were currently attending English Preparatory Classes. To collect data, the study utilized a mixed method including Willingness to Communicate Questionnaire (see Appendix A) and Self-perceived Communication Competence English Questionnaire (see Appendix B) on the Quantitative side and a semi-structured interview on the Qualitative.

4. Procedure

A two-fold procedure was adopted to carry out the present study. Initially, at the beginning of the second academic term of 2021-2022 education year, the necessary ethical approval (see Appendix C) was obtained from the institution aforementioned and consent forms (see Appendix D) were distributed to the students relevant. The study was totally on a voluntary basis. Later, a survey consisting of 204 respondents was carried out on the premises of the University of the Necmettin Erbakan, Konya-Turkey. Students at Necmettin Erbakan University School of Foreign Languages from different majors were given an on-line questionnaire regarding their horoscopes and their willingness to communicate plus their self-perceived communication competence in English. Both the Willingness to Communicate Scale (WTC) and the Self-perceived Communication Competence Scale (SPCC) had 12 items to evaluate the answers given by the students. It took a week to gather 204 answers from 10 different preparatory classes. The findings were put down by making use of *One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA)*. Following the questionnaire, in order to reinforce the findings, a semi-structured interview was conducted to 11 students of English language teaching preparatory class. The interview was transcribed and examined in depth via content analysis.

As for the qualitative part of the analysis, the following interview questions were directed to the students fore mentioned.

4.1. Semi-structured Interview Questions

1. What kind of a person do you think you are? What is your definition of yourself? What are your personal characteristics?
2. At times when you need to use English to communicate, how do you feel (Remember the times when you communicated in English, how did you feel?) Are you usually at ease or do you feel nervous? If so, why? Do you enjoy using English?
3. Are you an introvert or an extrovert? Would you consider this personality trait as affecting your willingness to communicate and how you communicate in English?
4. What is your horoscope? What are the general traits of it? Do you believe you reflect these traits, in what way?
5. In general, in which situation do you feel most willing to communicate in English? (In pairs, in small groups, in a whole class; with close friends, with teachers, with classmates (not close friends), etc.)

4.2. Population and Sampling

On the quantitative grounds, the present study was put through with 204 preparatory class students attending different departments of different faculties of Necmettin Erbakan University in Konya-Turkey. For the qualitative part, namely, the semi-structured interview, 11 students were conversed. In terms of sampling, convenience sampling, in which the participants are chosen based on their relative ease of access, was used (Wiederman, 1999). The 204 students were told about the research being carried out via the on-line questionnaire. Thereafter, they were informed about the research process in detail.

4.3. Data Collection

In this study, a questionnaire and a semi structured interview were utilized to collect data. The survey was formed online and sent to students via Google forms. Altogether, 204 students from 10 different preparatory classes participated in the survey. The second part of the study was the semi-structured interview. 11 students from the Education Faculty who also participated in the survey were given appointments according to their convenience. The students were told about the research being applied and were given the questions in advance. Within this process, five pre-prepared guiding questions were directed to the students whose answers were recorded later to be transcribed.

4.4. Data Analysis

In order to validate it, a mixed method design was determined for the current study. Brown, (2011) puts quantitative analysis in its simplest form as any study that counts things. He defines it as any research that focuses on counting things and on understanding the patterns that emerge from those counts. In view of the above stated definition, a descriptive study following a survey including 204 students was practiced as the first part of the data analysis. *One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA)* was used to demonstrate the findings of the survey. Stake (1995) illustrates analysis as a matter of giving meaning to first impressions as well as to final compositions, and interpreting our first impressions. As the study's Qualitative base, Content Analysis was used to analyze the data gathered from the semi-structured interview results. The gathered data was separated and conceptually categorized into meaningful chunks. (Yıldırım and Simsek, 2013). Through a very long process and with an in-depth attention, these categories were analyzed and the results found were interpreted.

5. Findings and Discussion

5.1. Findings pertaining to the first research question

In this part, the findings related to the first research question “Does B2 level preparatory students’ level of WTC differ according to; a) horoscopes, b) age, c) gender, d) faculty?” are presented.

Table 1: *One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) results by horoscope*

Horoscope	Statistic	Group Discussion	Interpersonal	Public Speaking	Acquaintance	Friend	WTC
Aquarius (n:20)	$\bar{X}$	61,00	56,67	53,00	57,00	57,13	54,54
Aries (n:13)	$\bar{X}$	70,51	68,97	55,38	64,62	65,77	62,95
Cancer (n:19)	$\bar{X}$	68,07	62,63	50,70	62,11	60,26	57,81
Capricorn (n:18)	$\bar{X}$	69,07	59,44	55,19	59,86	60,83	58,33
Gemini (n:15)	$\bar{X}$	61,78	62,22	53,33	62,00	58,33	56,72
Leo (n:23)	$\bar{X}$	70,87	65,22	52,46	63,80	65,43	60,11
Libra (n:18)	$\bar{X}$	64,26	67,78	47,59	58,61	59,72	57,96
Pisces (n:9)	$\bar{X}$	72,59	74,07	56,30	66,67	68,33	65,28
Sagittarius (n:15)	$\bar{X}$	60,44	62,44	51,33	57,33	59,67	55,50
Scorpio (n:23)	$\bar{X}$	70,72	61,45	55,51	63,91	64,13	59,02
Taurus (n:13)	$\bar{X}$	63,59	62,56	54,10	59,81	60,58	58,59
Virgo (n:17)	$\bar{X}$	69,02	68,63	58,04	65,88	67,94	63,24
	F	530	654	232	333	456	309
	P	,881	,780	,995	,978	,928	,983

Table 2: *Kruskal Wallis test results by horoscope*

Horoscope	Statistic	Meetings	Stranger
Aquarius (n:20)	$\bar{X}$	87,20	90,90
Aries (n:13)	$\bar{X}$	118,27	117,62
Cancer (n:19)	$\bar{X}$	100,13	98,32
Capricorn (n:18)	$\bar{X}$	101,33	110,42
Gemini (n:15)	$\bar{X}$	97,13	92,03
Leo (n:23)	$\bar{X}$	103,83	98,37
Libra (n:18)	$\bar{X}$	103,58	109,50
Pisces (n:9)	$\bar{X}$	116,22	125,61
Sagittarius (n:15)	$\bar{X}$	91,87	89,50
Scorpio (n:23)	$\bar{X}$	96,70	94,78
Taurus (n:13)	$\bar{X}$	107,69	108,19
Virgo (n:17)	$\bar{X}$	114,15	107,65
	χ^2	4,447	5,680
	P	,955	,894

When the participants' willingness to communicate in sub-categories and entire scale were examined in terms of their horoscopes (See Table 1 and 2), it was found that their scores did not change significantly according to their horoscopes. In other words, the participants' horoscopes had no effect on their willingness to communicate neither in sub-categories nor on the entire scale.

Table 3: *One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) results by age*

Sub-score	Age	N	$\bar{X}$	SS	SD	F	p	Sig. Difference
Public speaking	18	68	56,57	21,49	3,195	,470	,704	-
	20	106	52,36	23,93				
	21	16	52,08	29,74				
	22	9	52,96	26,48				
	Total	199	53,80	23,65				

Table 4: *Kruskal Wallis test results by age*

Age	Statistic	Group Discussion	Meetings	Interper.	Stranger	Acquain.	Friend	WTC
18 (n:68)	M.R.	108,51	110,24	107,12	105,79	110,73	109,45	109,25
20(n:106)	M.R.	95,07	94,51	92,68	95,54	93,94	94,36	94,41
21 (n:16)	M.R.	94,06	95,25	102,41	99,53	91,75	94,78	93,44
22 (n:9)	M.R.	104,39	95,78	128,17	109,67	104,94	104,33	107,61
	χ^2	2,493	3,276	4,947	1,580	3,933	3,035	3,119
	p	,477	,351	,176	,664	,269	,386	,374

When the participants' willingness to communicate in sub-categories and entire scale were examined in terms of their ages (See Table 3 and 4), it was found that their scores did not show a significant difference according to their ages. In other words, the participants' ages did not affect their willingness to communicate neither in sub-categories nor on the entire scale.

Table 5: *Independent samples t test results by gender*

Sub-score	Gender	N	$\bar{X}$	SD	df	t	P
Acquaintance	Female	111	61,53	21,42	201	-,092	,927
	Male	92	61,82	22,98			
Friend	Female	111	62,43	21,21	201	,188	,851
	Male	92	61,85	22,78			

Table 6: *Mann Whitney test results by gender*

Gender	Statistic	Group Discussion	Meetings	Interper.	Public S.	Stranger	WTC
Female (n:111)	M.R.	104,76	100,41	95,53	101,82	97,71	100,44
Male (n:92)	M.R.	98,67	103,92	109,80	102,22	107,18	103,88
	U	4800,000	4929,500	4388,000	5085,500	4629,500	4933,000
	p	,462	,671	,084	,961	,252	,678

As shown in Tables 5 and 6, the participants' scores in the sub-categories (group discussion, meetings, interpersonal, public speaking, and stranger) of WTC scale and entire scale did not differ significantly by gender. In other words, participants' gender does not affect their willingness to communicate in terms of neither the sub-categories nor the entire scale.

Table 7: *One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) results by faculty*

Faculty	Statistic	Acquaintance	WTC
Engineering Faculty (n:46)	$\bar{X}$	58,48	54,98
Faculty of Av. and Aero. Sciences (n:79)	$\bar{X}$	60,85	59,14
Faculty of Education (n:21)	$\bar{X}$	76,67	73,37
Faculty of Political Sciences (n:37)	$\bar{X}$	60,74	57,36
Faculty of Social S. and Humanities (n:20)	$\bar{X}$	58,13	54,21
	F	2,941	3,249
	P	,022	,013
	Sig. Difference	3-1, 3-2, 3-4, 3-5	3-1, 3-2, 3-4, 3-5

Table 8: *Kruskal Wallis test results by faculty*

Faculty	Statistic	Group Discussion	Meetings	Interper.	Public S.	Stranger	Friend
1*	M.R.	94,48	91,91	94,91	92,57	88,95	96,57
2*	M.R.	99,22	103,80	104,80	101,56	104,92	100,76
3*	M.R.	142,00	142,88	140,38	130,98	136,83	144,31

4*	M.R.	99,88	93,69	90,99	105,72	99,00	94,57
5*	M.R.	92,23	90,55	87,33	88,15	89,45	88,73
	χ^2	11,307	13,131	12,397	7,577	10,877	12,956
	p	,023	,011	,015	,108	,028	,011
	Sig.	3-1, 3-2,	3-1, 3-2,	3-1, 3-2,	-	3-1, 3-2,	3-1, 3-2,
	Difference	3-4,3-5	3-4,3-5	3-4,3-5		3-4,3-5	3-4,3-5

*1= Engineering Faculty, 2= Faculty of Av. and Aero. Sciences, 3= Faculty of Education, 4= Faculty of Political Sciences, 5= Faculty of Social S. and Humanities

As seen in Tables 7 and 8, the participants' willingness to communicate in English both in sub-categories and the entire scale significantly differed by faculty. As a result of the Mann Whitney Test, which was conducted to determine which binary groups were significantly different, it was revealed that the participants in the education faculty had higher willingness to communicate in English scores than the participants from other faculties both in all sub-categories of the scale and in the entire scale.

5.2. Findings of the participants' Self-Perceived Communication Competence levels according to their socio-demographic characteristics

In this section, the findings related to the second research question "Does B2 level preparatory students' level of SPCC differ according to; a) horoscopes, b) age, c) gender, d) faculty?" are presented.

Table 9: One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) results by horoscope

Horoscope	Statistic	Public	Meeting	Dyad	Acquaintance	SPCC
Aquarius (n:20)	$\bar{X}$	52,50	49,50	57,67	55,50	53,75
Aries (n:13)	$\bar{X}$	55,38	52,56	63,85	61,35	58,14
Cancer (n:19)	$\bar{X}$	57,54	51,40	68,42	61,05	59,82
Capricorn (n:18)	$\bar{X}$	51,67	47,96	61,85	55,97	54,58
Gemini (n:15)	$\bar{X}$	50,22	52,67	66,00	61,50	57,83
Leo (n:23)	$\bar{X}$	57,68	51,45	66,81	62,50	58,30
Libra (n:18)	$\bar{X}$	59,44	50,37	67,78	60,28	59,26
Pisces (n:9)	$\bar{X}$	73,33	60,74	71,48	69,17	68,70
Sagittarius (n:15)	$\bar{X}$	53,11	49,78	64,44	57,67	56,17
Scorpio (n:23)	$\bar{X}$	54,20	53,04	65,22	61,74	57,57
Taurus (n:13)	$\bar{X}$	58,97	53,33	65,64	59,23	59,81
Virgo (n:17)	$\bar{X}$	60,00	54,90	68,82	62,21	61,72
	F	,731	,229	,439	,321	,379
	P	,708	,995	,937	,981	,963

Table 10: Kruskal Wallis test results by horoscope

Horoscope	Statistic	Group	Stranger	Friend
Aquarius (n:20)	M.R.	89,48	88,45	86,28
Aries (n:13)	M.R.	105,42	100,35	99,31
Cancer (n:19)	M.R.	109,24	109,92	109,08
Capricorn (n:18)	M.R.	94,31	98,78	90,19
Gemini (n:15)	M.R.	110,30	94,97	105,53
Leo (n:23)	M.R.	95,17	95,30	100,91
Libra (n:18)	M.R.	102,14	105,06	105,72
Pisces (n:9)	M.R.	128,33	143,22	124,67
Sagittarius (n:15)	M.R.	97,57	98,37	97,03
Scorpio (n:23)	M.R.	97,87	94,70	101,33
Taurus (n:13)	M.R.	106,12	112,58	102,85
Virgo (n:17)	M.R.	108,35	108,97	114,21
	χ^2	4,443	7,555	4,792
	P	,955	,753	,941

When the participants' self-perceived communication competence levels were examined in terms of their horoscopes (See Tables 9 and 10), it was found that the participants' self-perceived communication competence levels did not significantly differ according to their horoscopes. In other words, the horoscope type of the participants did not have a statistically significant effect on their self-perceived communication competence levels neither in sub-categories nor in the entire scale.

Table 11: *One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) results by age*

Age	Statistic	Meeting	Dyad	Acquaintance	SPCC
18 (n:68)	$\bar{X}$	61,00	56,67	53,00	57,00
20 (n:106)	$\bar{X}$	70,51	68,97	55,38	64,62
21 (n:16)	$\bar{X}$	68,07	62,63	50,70	62,11
22 (n:9)	$\bar{X}$	69,07	59,44	55,19	59,86
	F	,922	1,413	,546	,906
	P	,431	,240	,651	,439

Table 12: *Kruskal Wallis test results by age*

Age	Statistic	Public	Group	Stranger	Friend
18 (n:68)	M.R.	105,43	107,43	105,63	108,94
20 (n:106)	M.R.	95,43	93,83	94,60	92,25
21 (n:16)	M.R.	105,19	105,22	108,16	110,63
22 (n:9)	M.R.	103,61	107,33	106,56	104,83
	χ^2	1,440	2,634	2,020	4,174
	P	,696	,452	,568	,243

As shown in Tables 11 and 12, the participants' self-perceived communication competence levels did not significantly differ according to their ages. This is all to say, the participants' ages did not have a significant effect on their self-perceived communication competence levels neither in sub-categories nor on the entire scale.

Table 13: *Independent samples t test results by gender*

Gender	Statistic	Dyad	Friend	SPCC
Female (n:111)	$\bar{X}$	64,35	62,55	56,77
Male (n:92)	$\bar{X}$	66,67	64,24	60,16
	<i>T</i>	-,755	-,541	4388,000
	P	,451	,589	,265

Table 14: *Mann Whitney test results by gender*

Gender	Statistic	Public	Meeting	Group	Stranger	Acquaintance
Female (n:111)	M.R.	98,05	95,56	98,98	105,79	100,06
Male (n:92)	M.R.	106,77	109,77	105,64	95,54	104,34
	U	4667,500	4391,000	4771,000	4147,000	4891,000
	P	,292	,086	,421	,021	,606

When the participants' self-perceived communication competence levels were examined in terms of their gender (See Tables 13 and 14), it was found that the participants' self-perceived communication competence levels did not significantly change according to their gender. In other words, the gender of the participants did not have a significant effect on their self-perceived communication competence levels neither in sub-categories nor in the entire scale.

Table 15: *One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) results by horoscope*

Faculty	Statistic	Friend	SPCC
Engineering Faculty (n:46)	$\bar{X}$	59,89	54,76
Faculty of Av. and Aero. Sciences (n:79)	$\bar{X}$	63,61	59,14

Faculty of Education (n:21)	$\bar{X}$	80,00	74,68
Faculty of Political Sciences (n:37)	$\bar{X}$	58,11	53,65
Faculty of Social S. and Humanities (n:20)	$\bar{X}$	62,13	54,63
	F	4,003	4,190
	p	,004	,003
	Sig. Difference	3-1,3-2,3-4,3-5	3-1,3-2,3-4,3-5

Table 16: *Kruskal Wallis test results by faculty*

Faculty	Statistic	Public	Meeting	Group	Dyad	Stranger	Acquaintance
1 (n:46)	M.R.	96,58	94,95	89,99	93,04	96,29	92,86
2 (n:79)	M.R.	103,82	101,14	104,84	102,82	104,81	102,09
3 (n:21)	M.R.	147,40	143,05	143,98	145,88	142,52	148,17
4 (n:37)	M.R.	87,85	91,49	89,84	90,16	87,80	90,42
5 (n:20)	M.R.	85,78	97,98	96,83	95,20	87,75	95,60
	χ^2	16,720	12,239	14,612	14,612	13,972	15,788
	P	,002	,016	,006	,006	,007	,003
	Sig. Difference	3-1, 3-2, 3-4, 3-5	3-1,3-2, 3-4,3-5	3-1,3-2, 3-4,3-5	3-1,3-2, 3-4,3-5	3-1,3-2, 3-4,3-5	3-1,3-2, 3-4,3-5

1= Engineering Faculty, 2= Faculty of Av. and Aero. Sciences, 3= Faculty of Education, 4= Faculty of Political Sciences, 5= Faculty of Social S. and Humanities

As can be seen in Tables 15 and 16, the participants' self-perceived communication levels significantly differed both in sub-categories and the entire scale of SPCC according to their faculty type. As a result of the Mann Whitney Test, which was conducted to determine which binary groups were significantly different, it was found that the participants in the education faculty had higher self-perceived communication competency than the participants from other faculties both in all sub-categories of the scale and in the entire scale.

5.3. Findings from semi-structured interviews

In this part, the findings obtained by analysing qualitative data were presented.

Figure 1: *Participants' feelings when they use English to communicate*

Figure 1 presents the feelings of the participants when they use English to communicate. As shown in the figure, the participants' feelings were classified into three themes: *feeling nervous and stressed* (f:6), *feeling happy and proud* (f:3), and *feeling comfortable and relaxed* (f:3). The theme "feeling nervous and stressed" was most frequently expressed by the participants. Regarding this theme, five codes were obtained: the lack of speaking practice, fearing of making mistakes, fluency and accuracy issues, personality-related barriers, and lecture-related outcomes. The first theme was followed by the one entitled with "feeling happy and proud" in which two codes

“the pleasure of expressing our feelings in a different language, the satisfaction of learning a new language” were obtained. In the final theme “feeling comfortable and relaxed,” two codes were found: *Happiness in using learned knowledge and loving the target language.*

Some excerpts of the participants' opinions for the themes were as follows:

“Generally, I feel nervous when I need to use English to communicate. Because I think I don't have enough chance to use English in my daily life.” (P4)

“...when I have to make a presentation or talk with a teacher, I feel nervous and excited, and I think the reason of this is related to my personal characteristics...” (P9)

“The expressions are extremely important in the interaction on the other hand finding correct vocabulary can be difficult. I'm trying to solve this problem with using elementary words. I feel nervous and willing.” (P10)

“I have always been very happy to be able to speak English. The idea of being able to express yourself in another language has always seemed unique to me. I can say that I feel comfortable while speaking English.” (P11)

“I feel very excited because I love speaking English and when I speak, I feel so comfortable and relaxed.” (P1)

Table 17: Participants' personality traits and their effects on speaking

Are you an introvert or an extrovert?		Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Introvert		4	33,33
Extrovert		5	41,67
Both (Depends on the situation)		3	25,00
Does this personality trait affect your communication in English?		Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Yes		11	91,67
No		1	8,33
Effects/ Personality	Introvert	Extrovert	Both
Effects of personality on speaking	Lagging behind in speaking	Advancing self-confidence in speaking	Not having direct effect
	Having less social skills	Being enthusiastic to speak English	
	Feeling anxious while speaking		

Table 17 displays the personality traits of the participants as well as their effects on speaking. When asked if they were introverts or extroverts, 5 participants stated “Extrovert,” 4 participants stated “Introvert” and 3 participants stated “both”. A large proportion of the participants (%91,67) stated that their personality trait affected their communication in English. When the expressions of the participants were examined, three codes were found for introvert, two for extrovert, and one code for both, regarding the effect of their personalities on speaking. It was noted that all of the codes pertaining to introverts covered negative remarks. Among these codes, the most expressed code was lagging behind in speaking (f:3). This code was followed by the codes of having less social skills and feeling anxious while speaking, respectively. The extrovert codes included *advancing self-confidence in speaking* and *being enthusiastic to speak English*. The code "advancing self-confidence in speaking" was the most frequently expressed by participants among these codes (f:4). Participants who commented on their personalities as both claimed that their personalities had no direct influence on their speaking.

Some excerpts of the participants' opinions for the themes were as follows:

“As I said before, I'm an extrovert person, I can easily make friends. I think being an extrovert person affects the willingness to communicate in English, because extrovert people can speak without being ashamed and they want to speak a lot, but introvert people are very shy, and they can't speak so much, not even with their families.”

“I can say that I am an introvert without thinking. I prefer staying at home to going out with people. And I think it has a huge effect on communicating, especially communicating in English. Because introverts tend to have less social skills than extroverts, thus, this makes speaking English hard for the introverts.” (P5)

“I am usually an extrovert. I am not afraid to interact with people. I also try not to be shy about speaking English. Being an extrovert helps me a lot to talk to people comfortably.” (P8)

“I am an introverted person and I think it affects my communication with people, but I don’t think it is a willingness because I am willing to talk most of the time, but I don’t feel comfy enough to do so.” (P9)

Table 18: Participants’ horoscopes and the states of reflecting the traits of the horoscopes

Participant	Horoscope	Positive traits (Participant ideas)	Negative traits (Participant ideas)
P4, P5, P7, P8	Leo	self-confident, leader/guide, helpful, perfectionist, ambitious	arrogant, reckless
P3, P10	Sagittarius	Enthusiastic, determined and fond of independence	Impatient and careless
P11, P12	Libra	balanced, fair, passionate, talented, funny	-
P2	Gemini	Social, talkative,	whimsical, indecisive and nosy
P1	Aquarius	Progressive, idealistic, intelligent and creative	-
P9	Scorpio	Bellicose, powerful, ambitious	
		Frequency (f)	Percentage (%) Participants
		6	54,55 P1,P3,P8,P9,P10,P12
		3	27,27 P2,P4,P11
		2	18,18 P5,P7

Table 18 shows the horoscopes of the participants and the states of reflecting the traits of the horoscopes. Four Leo participants offered seven personality traits, five of which were positive (self-confident, leader/guide, helpful, perfectionist, ambitious) and two of which were negative (arrogant, reckless). Two Sagittarius participants mentioned general personality traits. They expressed five general personality traits, three of them positive (enthusiastic, determined and fond of independence) and two of them negative (impatient and careless). Two participants who voiced their thoughts about Libra indicated five general personality traits (balanced, fair, passionate, talented, funny) that were all positive. The Gemini participant expressed five general personality traits, two of which were positive (social and talkative) and three of which were negative (whimsical, indecisive, and nosy). One participant each gave an opinion for Aquarius and Scorpio signs; the participants stated four general personality traits (progressive, idealistic, intelligent, and creative) in Aquarius and three general personality traits (bellicose, powerful, ambitious) in Scorpio. When the opinions of the participants about the general personality traits of their horoscopes were examined, it was discovered that 6 participants believed they had all the characteristics of their horoscopes, 3 participants stated that they had most/some characteristics of their horoscopes, and 2 participants thought that they did not have any characteristic of their horoscopes.

Some excerpts of the participants' opinions for the themes were as follows:

“It’s Gemini. Gemini traits are more varied than those of other astrological signs. They can be social, talkative, and whimsical but they can also be indecisive or nosy. I do reflect almost all of them except than being talkative all the time.” (P2)

“My horoscope is Sagittarius. General characteristics of Sagittarius an enthusiastic, determined but sometimes impatient and careless person. These traits just reflect me.” (P3)

“My zodiac sign is Leo. We can define Leos as confident. They love to take the lead when they have the chance. And it is said that they love themselves to death. To be honest, I don’t believe in horoscopes that much because I don’t have the same traits with other Leos. I can’t say that I am confident, and I dislike taking the lead.” (P5)

“My zodiac sign is Scorpio. General traits of Scorpio zodiac sign as bellicose, powerful, and ambitious. I think I reflect these traits because when I look at my life, I can see I am a person who has these personal traits.” (P9)

“My horoscope is Libra. They say Libras are the most balanced, fair, passionate. In my opinion I reflect most of Libra traits.” (P11)

Figure 2: Situations participants feel most willing to communicate in English

Figure 2 depicts the situations in which participants feel most willing to communicate in English. The opinions of the participants were grouped under five themes. Among these themes, “Feeling more comfortable with close friends” was the most expressed one by the participants (f:5). In this theme, the participants pointed out that speaking with their close friends enabled them to feel more comfortable while speaking English. The situation that followed the close friends of the participants in terms of feeling more comfortable while speaking English was their classmates(f:4). Some participants reported that their classmates were a supportive force in feeling comfortable speaking English. Another situation that emerged in this regard was that they felt more relaxed in small groups (f:4). This finding revealed that the participants did not feel equally at ease speaking in front of large groups. Some participants emphasized that they felt more pleasant speaking with teachers in English (f:2). In this theme, the participants showed that their teachers were more understanding when it came to tolerating their mistakes and encouraging them to speak up. One participant noted that speaking in pairs helped her feel more pleased (f:1).

Some excerpts of the participants' opinions for the themes were as follows:

“Like I’ve said before, I feel nervous whenever I talk English in front of my teachers. I feel comfortable when I communicate in English with my close friends.” (P3)

“Generally, I feel most willing to communicate in English when I am with my friends or classmates.” (P9)

“I feel most willing to communicate in English generally in small groups, in front of the few people.” (P7)

“I feel more comfortable speaking English with teachers because I know that even if I make mistakes, they will not judge me or belittle me.” (P8)

“I believe that pair work is the most effective way to practice English since it gives learners more speaking time. I do feel the most comfortable when I work in pairs too because there’s only one person, I need to explain myself.” (P1)

The assumption that led to the investigation of this article was whether the months the students were born in, that is, their horoscopes influenced their willingness to communicate in English. The study set off with 3 research questions. The first of which aimed to find an answer to whether B2 level preparatory students’ level of WTC differed according to their a) horoscopes, b) age, c) gender, d) faculty. On the contrary to what was assumed, the students showed no tendency to communicate according to their horoscopes. The only variable that had a significant effect statistically was the faculty of the students. The preparatory students of the education faculty tended to have a significantly higher level of willingness to communicate. When looked back at the literature, similarly, Ahmed (2006), found that no horoscope in particular highlighted a frequency count or a percentage of significance for his hypothesis that individuals whose horoscopes subsume personal qualities and characteristics have interest in English.

The second question in research was the perceptions of B2 level preparatory class students of their willingness to communicate (WTC) in English according to their socio-demographic characteristics. As a result of the Mann Whitney Test, which was conducted to determine which binary groups were significantly different, it was found that the participants in the education faculty had higher self-perceived communication competency than the participants from other faculties both in all sub-categories and in the entire scale.

To find an answer to the last research question to what the relationship was between B2 level preparatory class students’ WTC in English and date of birth (horoscope), a semi structured interview was acted out with 11 preparatory class students of the education faculty. How willing the students of different horoscopes were in communicating and how they perceived themselves in interaction atmospheres was the first case in question. The students’ feelings were classified into three themes: *feeling nervous and stressed (f:6)*, *feeling happy and proud(f:3)*, and *feeling comfortable and relaxed(f:3)*. The theme “feeling nervous and stressed” was most frequently expressed by the participants. Six students out of eleven stated that what made them unwilling to communicate in English was being nervous and stressed when doing so. Subsequently, a large proportion of the participants (%91,67) stated that their personality trait affected their communication in English. They were asked to define themselves as introverts or extroverts. Five of them expressed themselves as extroverts which showed their will and enthusiasm when communicating in English. Previous studies also demonstrated that personality has a moderately significant correlation with WTC (McCroskey & Richmond, 1990; Şener, 2014; Yashima et al., 2004, Öz, 2014) or an indirect affect on WTC (MacIntyre, 2007; MacIntyre & Charos, 1996).

When the answers of the students in the interview were examined, the most communicative horoscope was found to be the Leo. 4 students out of 11 gave positive traits going hand in hand with their will and confidence in communicative activities. One student who was a Gemini also claimed to be social and talkative. The remaining horoscopes belonging to the rest of the students showed no relevance with the related topic. Although no significant effect was observed in the statistical part of the study, the qualitative data elaborated to some extent that among the 5 other stated horoscopes, Leos were more willing to communicate with their friends, with their classmates and with strangers. Based on this discussion, it can be suggested that teachers should pay closer attention to their students’ personality features, and should be able to provide a variety of different communicative activities that would be appealing for both extroverts and introverts in class.

6. Pedagogical Implications

Individual differences have always been an important factor in language teaching. These factors can be anything from learning aptitude, cultural background to age, gender, and personality. As Ehrman, Leaver and Oxford (2003) put it, learner differences include, among others, factors classified under three areas. Learning styles, learning

strategies and affective variables. The third research area, namely, affective variables was the starting point of the present study. As ELT practitioners, possible interventions that could be incorporated into instructional pedagogy should always be contemplated. It was this thought that gave a prompt to conduct a study to ascertain the relevance between the horoscopes and the willingness to communicate of students. Horoscopes are considered by many nowadays to be thoroughly affecting the characteristics of individuals. Each horoscope tends to harbour a variety of feature within itself, so believe it or not, the month and hour you are born in actually innately gives you a gift of traits. Interpreting horoscopes to identify learning styles is an area of research carried out by Raggini (2019). She points out that the predictions made in the horoscopes regarding the students' language learning abilities were found to be true to a greater level. (Raggini 2019). It is implied in the present study that students who are more social, extrovert, self-confident, talkative and ambitious are those of certain horoscopes which make them much more willing to communicate in language learning. Yet, the lack of some horoscopes such as Aries and Pisces within the group being interviewed can be considered as a shortcoming.

7. Conclusion

The present study having a mixed method approach shed light to the literature by examining the influence of horoscopes on Turkish preparatory class students' willingness to communicate in English and the factors affecting it. The variable being in issue for this study was horoscopes. Does it affect students' willingness to communicate, if so, in what way. Statistical results showed that horoscopes had no significant affect on the level of the participating students' willingness to communicate who were enrolled in B2 level classes of English preparatory program at a state university. The relationship between their WTC and age, gender, horoscopes was not found to be statistically significant apart from faculty. This was assumed to be partly because the students of Education Faculty had a higher level of linguistic proficiency, motivation and probably communicatively more competent than the remaining faculties. However, the interview results gave a deeper insight in some of these areas. For instance, when students were asked about their personality and how they think it affected their communication in English and their willingness to communicate, their answers showed diversity. The adjectives and prompts they used to define themselves gave clear evidence and a direct relevance with the general traits of their horoscopes. Herewith, subsequent to the findings and processes outlined above, it can be concluded from the current study that L2 WTC is a multilayered Notion which is intricately interconnected with linguistic, affective, individual and contextual, factors (Cao, 2011; Peng, 2020) within which horoscopes do have a somewhat significant role. The study is not an acknowledgement of astrology but only a shout out to science, which has come up with more than a few examples. It is an effort to reveal the way our birthdates might influence our personalities which indirectly plays a great role on our willingness to communicate. However, there is still plenty of room for more research to assure some of the findings on this list.

Conflicts of interest

The author has not declared any conflicts of interest.

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Appendix 1: Willingness to Communicate Scale (WTC)

- _____ 1. Have a small-group conversation in English with acquaintances.
- _____ 2. Give a presentation in English to a group of strangers.
- _____ 3. Give a presentation in English to a group of friends.
- _____ 4. Talk in English a large meeting among strangers.
- _____ 5. Have a small-group conversation in English with strangers.
- _____ 6. Talk in English in a large meeting among friends.
- _____ 7. Talk in English to friends.
- _____ 8. Talk in English in a large meeting with acquaintances.
- _____ 9. Talk in English to acquaintances.
- _____ 10. Give a presentation in English to a group of acquaintances

Appendix 2: Self-perceived Communication Competence Scale (SPCC)

- _____ 1. Present a talk to a group of strangers.
- _____ 2. Talk with an acquaintance.
- _____ 3. Talk in a large meeting of friends.
- _____ 4. Talk in a small group of strangers.
- _____ 5. Talk with a friend.
- _____ 6. Talk in a large meeting of acquaintances.
- _____ 7. Talk with a stranger.
- _____ 8. Present a talk to a group of friends.
- _____ 9. Talk in a small group of acquaintances.
- _____ 10. Talk in a large meeting of strangers.
- _____ 11. Talk in a small group of friends.
- _____ 12. Present a talk to a group of acquaintances.

Appendix 3: Ethical Approval

NECMETTİN ERBAKAN ÜNİVERSİTESİ
SOSYAL VE BEŞERİ BİLİMLER BİLİMSEL ARAŞTIRMALAR ETİK KURULU
BAŞKANLIĞI
ETİK KURUL KARARI

Etik Kurul Toplantı Tarihi/Sayısı ve Karar No	Tarih :08/04/2022 Toplantı Sayısı:04 Karar No :2022/148
Araştırmanın Başlığı	The Influence Of Horoscopes On Preparatory Class Students' Willingness To Communicate
Sorumlu Araştırmacı	Dr. Öğr. Üyesi Feyza Nur EKİZER
Etik Kurul Kararı	9191 sayılı başvuru değerlendirilmiş olup, araştırma Etik Kurul tarafından uygun görülmüştür.

ASLI GİBİDİR
08/04/2022

Doç. Dr. Ahmet KURNAZ
Etik Kurul Başkanı

Appendix 4: Consent Form

NECMETTİN ERBAKAN ÜNİVERSİTESİ
SOSYAL VE BEŞERİ BİLİMLER BİLİMSEL ARAŞTIRMALAR ETİK KURULU
GÖNÜLLÜ KATILIMCI ONAY FORMU
(Katılımcı Bilgisi Olmadan Doldurulmalıdır)

Sizi _____ tarafından yürütülen “ _____ ” başlıklı araştırmaya davet ediyoruz. Bu araştırmanın amacı _____ dir. Araştırmada sizden tahminen ___ dakika ayırmanız istenmektedir.

Bu çalışmaya katılmak tamamen GÖNÜLLÜLÜK esasına dayanmaktadır.

Çalışmanın amacına ulaşması için sizden beklenen, bütün sorulara, kimsenin baskısı veya telkini altında olmadan, size en uygun gelen cevapları içtenlikle vermenizdir. Bu formu okuyup onaylamanız, araştırmaya katılmayı kabul ettiğiniz anlamına gelecektir. Ancak, çalışmaya katılmama veya katıldıktan sonra herhangi bir anda çalışmayı bırakma hakkına da sahiptir.

Bu çalışmadan elde edilecek bilgiler tamamen araştırma amacı ile kullanılacak olup KİŞİSEL BİLGİLERİNİZ GİZLİ TUTULACAKTIR; ancak verileriniz yayın amacı ile kullanılabilir.

Eğer araştırmanın amacı ile ilgili verilen bu bilgiler dışında, şimdi veya sonra daha fazla bilgiye ihtiyaç duyarsanız, araştırmacıya şimdi sorabilir veya aşağıdaki iletişim bilgilerinden ulaşabilirsiniz.

Yardımcı Araştırmacı/Sorumlu Araştırmacı Tarafından Doldurulacak	
Katılımcının kişisel bilgilerinin gizli tutulacağını, katılımcının çalışma kapsamında sağlayacağı tüm verilerin etik kurallara göre işleneceğini ve bu etik kuralların ihlali durumunda, ortaya çıkacak tüm sorumluluğu kabul ettiğimi beyan ederim.	
Unvanı, Adı-Soyadı:	_____
Tarih:	_____
İmza:	_____
Yetişkin Katılımcının Kendisi tarafından doldurulacak	
☐ Yukarıda yer alan ve araştırmadan önce katılımcıya verilmesi gereken bilgileri okudum ve katılmam istenen çalışmanın kapsamını ve amacını, gönüllü olarak üzerime düşen sorumlulukları anladım. ☐ Çalışma hakkında yazılı/sözlü açıklama araştırmacı tarafından yapıldı ve kişisel bilgilerimin özenle korunacağı konusunda yeterli güven verildi. ☐ Bu koşullarda, araştırmaya kendi isteğimle, hiçbir baskı ve telkin olmaksızın katılmayı kabul ediyorum.	
18 Yaş Altı Kısıtlı Katılımcının Velisi/Vasisi tarafından doldurulacak	
☐ Yukarıda yer alan ve araştırmadan önce katılımcıya verilmesi gereken bilgileri okudum ve bu çalışmanın kapsamını ve amacını, gönüllü katılımcılara düşen sorumlulukları anladım. ☐ Çalışma hakkında yazılı/sözlü açıklama araştırmacı tarafından yapıldı ve katılımcının kişisel bilgilerinin özenle korunacağı konusunda yeterli güven verildi. ☐ Bu koşullarda, Velisi/Vasisi bulunduğum _____'nin araştırmaya kendi isteğimle, hiçbir baskı ve telkin olmaksızın katılmasını kabul ediyorum.	
Araştırma tamamlandığında genel/özel sonuçların benimle paylaşılmasını	☐ İstiyorum ☐ İstemiyorum

Adı-Soyadı: veya Katılımcı Kodu:	
Tarih:	
İmza:	
İletişim Bilgileri (İsteğe bağlı):	

Bu form, katılımcının kendisi/velisi/vasisi tarafından imzalandıktan sonra araştırmacıya teslim edilecektir. Ayrıca talep edildiği takdirde, bu formun bir nüshası katılımcıya verilecektir.